

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Keep Wales Tidy and Keep Scotland Beautiful

Towards Data-Driven
Litter-Free Streets

**20 February -
3 March 2023**

Contents

1	Executive Summary	2
1.1	Challenge Overview	3
1.2	Data Overview	5
1.3	Main Aim and Objectives	9
1.4	Approach	10
1.5	Main Conclusions	10
1.6	Limitations	11
1.7	Recommendations and Future Work	11
2	Review of Literature	12
3	Data Overview	13
3.1	Dataset Description	13
3.2	Data Quality Issues	14
3.3	Data Summary	16
4	Experiments	16
4.1	The TACO Dataset	17
4.2	Explored Machine Learning Frameworks and Models	18
4.3	Experiments and Results	19
5	Future Work and Research Avenues	23
6	Conclusions	25
7	Team members	25
	References	26

1 Executive Summary

This data study involved the use of litter datasets to establish a focused proof of concept (PoC) for automatic litter detection that can potentially replace the manual component of the local environmental audit and management system (LEAMS) methodology. Specifically, the study has been carried out using several datasets comprising over 16,800 images of various types and having various levels of annotations. The images were broadly categorised into (1) Images with complete annotation, (2) Images with incomplete annotation, (3) Duplicate images and (4) Non-duplicate images. To better evaluate the datasets, an initial systematic data analysis was performed to identify any potential distinctions and/or similarities between the various subsets of the datasets. In particular, the distribution of the annotations and categories, as well as any potential biases were taken into consideration during the initial systematic data analysis. The initial analysis allowed for a more robust preparation of the datasets for the data study.

Following a review of the literature to identify past, current, and state-of-the-art approaches for the building of object detection models for the automatic detection of litter, several models were built and tested to allow for a comparison of their accuracies and efficiencies under various annotation techniques. The models built include mask R-CNN (region-based convolutional neural network), fast R-CNN, YOLO (you only look once), and DETR (detection transformer) models. The performance metric used for their evaluation in terms of object detection is mainly the mean average precision (mAP) with an IoU (Intersection over Union) threshold of 0.5. It should be noted that the higher the mAP, the more precise and the higher the recall of the object detection model. However, for classification, the F1 score was mostly used because it offers a good balance between precision and recall metrics.

One-class litter detection and six-class classification problems were formulated and addressed. For both problems, DETR with a backbone of ResNet-50 (a 50-layer convolutional neural network with 48 convolutional layers, one MaxPool layer, and one average pool layer) showed the highest mAP of 51.2 and 16.1 for the one-class litter and six-class classification problems, respectively, whereas mask R-CNN showed the

least mAP of 27.6 and 6.1 for the one-class litter and six-class classification problems, respectively. It should be noted that due to the brevity of the data study group (DSG) event, hyperparameter tuning or optimisation was neither explored nor exploited by the participants. It should also be noted that aside from the experiments mentioned above, models were also built using YOLO (you only look once) algorithms. The results also indicate that these models can be employed satisfactorily for object detection (i.e., litter detection).

1.1 Challenge Overview

Automatic litter detection remains a much sought-after innovation with the goal of augmenting current manual techniques for surveying and evaluating the cleanliness of different areas of built and rural environments and identifying various locations where action may be required to manage and/or reduce litter. Keep Wales Tidy and Keep Scotland Beautiful (KWT-KSB) are charities based in the U.K. that are interested in the potential that data-driven and artificial intelligence (AI) based paradigms and modelling tools can offer in the design and development of automatic litter analysis and detection systems.

Currently, manual survey systems such as LEAMS used by KWT-KSB already provide a standardised and conventional approach for local authorities to run checks on their statutory duty to keep public areas and spaces free of litter. However, staffing limitations mean that litter surveys are not produced frequently, and when available, they are fraught with high levels of subjectivity in terms of geolocations, the areas covered, and several other factors, such as the inability to assess large areas expeditiously, making the possibility of real-time data analysis and visualisation nearly impossible. Hence, the overall goal of litter monitoring and reduction is hampered in a way. Automatic litter detection can potentially help to address these bottlenecks as demonstrated in the literature. However, the practicality of such a system is still very much embryonic.

To demonstrate and validate a PoC for an automatic litter detection system, the Alan Turing Institute and KWT-KSB have proposed the design and development of an intelligent survey system whose practicality is to

be exemplified using various litter datasets that include the 2019 open-source TACO (trash annotations in context) dataset [1], the 2022 open-source PlastOPol dataset for litter detection [2, 3], and example images owned by KWT-KSB with their associated annotations in COCO (common objects in context) format [4]. Further to the above, the images are labelled such that each object is surrounded by bounding boxes (i.e., feature detection in images). Therefore, the DSG participants are expected to rigorously apply existing image processing and machine learning techniques in creative and novel ways.

Hybridisation of the machine learning methods was also anticipated to be carried out by the DSG participants to generate new outcomes and/or propose novel paradigms. Some of the specialist areas that constitute the premise of the study included (but were not limited to) image processing (using algorithmic frameworks and signal processing routines) for image correction, image resolution manipulation, deep learning (e.g., using convolutional neural network (CNN)-based methodologies such as region-based CNN and others) for image classification, computer vision and object detection, and dataset augmentation paradigms (for example, using generative adversarial network-based, others) for robustness and generalisation.

For the challenge, many of the above methods and other closely related methods are investigated under various surveying scenarios, such as different weather conditions, imagery sources, or different methods of data capture to produce an output reliable enough to be as effective as a LEAMS score. Further explorations accommodated difficulties in object recognition, object masking (e.g., license plates, people, faces, etc.), and geo-referencing development such that maps of areas requiring intervention can be produced and easily accessed by KWT-KSB staff. The input to the automatic litter detection system will be a series of images taken at an angle downwards, approximately every 4 metres along a 50-metre stretch of pavement. The proposal is that once this system is in place, cameras can be attached to garbage trucks or dustbin vans, and regular data can be produced for the majority of relevant areas.

1.2 Data Overview

1.2.1 Training Data

The datasets detailed in Table 1 have been used as the training data for the DSG challenge.

Datasets	Segmentation	Bounding-Box	Classes	Images	Annotation	Source
TACO	✓	✓	✓	1500	4784	Open
PlastOPol	✓	✓	X	2418	2418	Open
Kili's	X	✓	X	4260	14917	Open
Unannotated	X	X	X	1848	0	KWT
Synthetic	✓	✓	✓	130000	130000	KWT

Table 1: An overview of the datasets.

1.2.2 Open-Source Datasets

Kili's dataset [5], the TACO dataset [1], and the PlastOPol dataset [2, 3] are all open-source datasets that offer several advantages for machine learning and AI applications. One of the main advantages of open-source datasets like these is that they are freely available for public use, which promotes transparency, collaboration, and innovation in the field of machine learning. Researchers, developers, and other stakeholders can access the data, use it to train algorithms and develop new applications without any restrictions or fees. In addition to the aforesaid, open-source datasets such as Kili's dataset [5], TACO dataset [1], and PlastOPol dataset [2, 3] are often curated and annotated to ensure high-quality and accuracy for machine learning applications. This saves both time and resources for researchers and developers who might otherwise need to collect and annotate their own datasets.

The curated and annotated images in Kili's dataset can be used for various computer vision tasks, including object detection, image classification, and segmentation. The TACO dataset [1] is an image dataset of waste in the wild that can potentially assist in wildlife conservation. The PlastOPol dataset focuses on detecting microplastics in environmental samples [2, 3], which is critical for understanding the impact of plastic pollution on the environment. To summarise, the advantages of open-source datasets such as Kili's dataset [5], TACO

dataset [1], and PlastOPol dataset [2,3] include (but are not limited to) the promotion of transparency, collaboration, and innovation, as well as the availability of curated and annotated data for machine learning and AI applications. Similar to other open-source datasets, the inherent limitation in these datasets is that the DSG participants had no control over the experiments employed for the generation and subsequent curation of the datasets. In addition to this limitation, the number of observations in the data sets is also limited to what is available from their respective sources.

1.2.3 Annotation Format

The annotations format is the same used for COCO (Common Objects in Context) Annotations [4]. These annotations are in the .json format and a .txt format that contains nested dictionaries. These nested dictionaries include a section for info (metadata), images (image identification number, location, and size), categories (including category number and name), and annotations (including the image identification number, where the annotation is located, the category identification number of the annotation, and the bounding box in the format $(x_{min}, y_{min}, (x_{max} - x_{min}), (y_{max} - y_{min}))$ (where x_{min} and y_{min} are the coordinates of the top left corner of the bounding box/rectangle, and x_{max} and y_{max} are the coordinates of the bottom right corner of the bounding box/rectangle, and the segmentation (i.e., a line tracing around the object) in the format $(x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2, x_3, y_3, \dots)$ where $x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2, x_3, y_3, \dots$ are the respective ordered pairs.

1.2.4 Supplementary Data

Aside from the open-source datasets recommended for the DSG challenge, the challenge owners (COs) provided supplementary datasets looking at graffiti and dog fouling, in anticipation that these would provide further information on the cleanliness of an area and hence increase the accuracy of the cleanliness estimate at a given location. Additional details on the supplementary datasets are provided in Table 2.

Dataset name	Positive examples	Negative examples
Dog Fouling	141	1,289
Bagged Dog Fouling	63	1,289
Graffiti	451	977

Table 2: An overview of the supplementary datasets.

1.2.5 Test Data

The primary test data for the DSG challenge comprised a street survey taken around the King's Buildings (KB), the main campus of the College of Science and Engineering at the University of Edinburgh, with 834 images in 22 different transects, each approximately 50 m long and having no overlaps between the respective images. It should be noted that the test data was provided by the COs (i.e., KWT-KSB).

1.2.6 Data Quality

As is typically found in many investigative studies involving data, the data used for the DSG challenge were of variable quality and the images in the respective datasets were in a range of sizes and resolutions. For example, Kili's dataset was generally poorer in terms of resolution and had fewer data classes (only four data classes, compared to the 60 data classes within the TACO dataset). The TACO dataset also had some unofficial annotations, which had not been checked by the research team prior to being published. However, the test data was of consistent size and resolution. This is alongside the fact that there was a range of different numbers of annotations for the different classes contained in the TACO dataset. A summary of this is shown in Figure 1 for the annotations of the TACO dataset.

1.2.7 Different Data Formats

The fact that the data comprised several datasets made the data difficult to parse. This was because the annotations were available in different .json files, and the category labels were also different (see Section 1.2.8). In addition, different datasets were missing different annotations (e.g., Kili's

dataset did not have segmentation and the PlastOPol dataset had different classes). Finally, the TACO and Kili's datasets contained multiple objects in single images, whereas the other data sources did not.

1.2.8 Category Labels

The TACO dataset contained 60 category labels, giving it the widest range of labels amongst all the datasets available for the DSG challenge [1]. The synthetic data employed the TACO labels along with seven extra labels (not originally included in the TACO dataset), which were added to have litter categories corresponding to the LEAMS survey system. This is explained as follows:

- Distinguishing between alcoholic and non-alcoholic drinks packaging, recyclable and non-recyclable paper, ferrous and non-ferrous aerosols, ferrous and non-ferrous metals, avoidable and unavoidable food waste.
- Adding cardboard food packaging instead of the wider TACO category "other carton".
- Adding "dog fouling" as a category.

These categories mostly differ because the distinction between (for example) alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages is important from the standpoint of pushing for societal change, and for recording possible methods for reducing social problems that may stem from alcoholism. The distinction between recyclable and non-recyclable paper is important for environmental reasons in terms of the attainment of sustainable development goals. However, from a computer vision point of view, there is very little difference in appearance between these categories, so, for simplicity, these categories are combined. The TACO categories have been used for the DSG challenge. Note that the other datasets had fewer labels. For example, the PlastOPol dataset only distinguished between "litter" and "not litter", and the Kili dataset had four data labels: "plastic bottle", "plastic bag", "other plastic waste", and "non-plastic waste" [2,3].

1.2.9 Synthetic Data

The synthetic data comprised images of different classes of litter in front of a green screen in different folders according to the class, with the folder label being the identification number of that class according to the labelling system. This was supplemented with background images that contained no litter. By automatically separating the foreground (litter) from the background, this provided the ability to undertake automatic segmentation around the litter object as well as the ability to implement data augmentation easily (by distorting the foreground image, rotating it, or doing other transformations to it while keeping the background image consistent). With 650 greenscreen images and 200 background images, a total of 130,000 image combinations can be generated for the computer to use as training data.

1.2.10 Unannotated Dataset

This data consisted of images with no labels or context for various street scenes, some of which contained litter and others which did not. In total, there were over 2,000 images in the unannotated dataset provided by KWT-KSB.

1.3 Main Aim and Objectives

The main aim of the project is to explore the possibility of implementing a machine learning system that can evaluate the cleanliness of an area automatically using a set of captured images of that area. To achieve this, it is anticipated that the machine learning system will mirror the existing and more conventional local environmental audit and management system (LEAMS) methodology, and the following objectives are set:

- Exploration of machine learning techniques and methodologies for the identification and/or detection of litter in captured images.
- Application of the most promising machine learning techniques and methodologies to a systematically consolidated database of environmental images to build and train litter classification and detection models.

- Optimisation and evaluation of the performance of the trained litter models to ascertain their practicality and optimality in real-world scenarios and contexts.
- Making a strong and relevant case for a fully operational litter classification and detection system where an optimal litter classification or detection model can be deployed effectively and efficiently.

1.4 Approach

A multi-stage approach has been adopted, where the model would initially be trained on the TACO dataset, and then successively trained on the other datasets to add to the size of the dataset. To start with, the TACO dataset alone was used to train and build models, as it is more robust and can be used for object detection as well as segmentation [1]. After achieving acceptable performance, the best model was to be selected and applied to Kili's dataset [5], then subsequently to the PlastOPol dataset [2, 3] to classify each image. The next stage then would involve increasing the size of the dataset by placing all datasets, including the synthetic data, into a single .json file. The model would then be trained on this combined dataset and after tuning the model and achieving satisfactory performance, further improvements can be made by assessing the model's performance on the unannotated dataset. Predictions are to be produced for the unannotated dataset and added to the dataset. Additionally, graffiti and dog fouling datasets were also to be employed to train and build another model and, if effective, combined with the main model.

As stated above, the approach can be summarily described as ensemble learning [6]. However, due to the brevity of the DSG challenge, only the first stage of the planned approach was implemented adequately to have some initial results or preliminary results.

1.5 Main Conclusions

In this study, a review of the literature has been carried out to identify popular and widely used machine learning (ML) techniques and methodologies for object detection with a strong focus on litter

classification and detection. These ML techniques and methodologies were then investigated for the identification and/or detection of litter in captured images by training and building several models on the TACO dataset. The models resulting from the investigations show that automatic litter detection and classification can be achieved in the context used for the experiments. However, additional work is still required to ensure the generalisation and robustness of the investigated methods and methodologies in the contexts of litter detection and classification.

1.6 Limitations

One of the major limitations of the work carried out is that the trained models have not been fine-tuned and their accuracies have not been validated over a broader spectrum that involves more dynamic and complex problem formulations such as those enumerated in Section 1.4. Another limitation is that the straightforward approach of employing existing techniques and methodologies for model construction and training somewhat de-emphasises the need to design and develop novel algorithms and paradigms. As a result, the innovation of the work simply lies in the use of existing methods for potential new applications. So, the second, third, and fourth objectives (see Section 1.3) are yet to be fully met based on the work carried out so far. This is because the time constraints imposed by the brevity of the DSG challenge somewhat limited the scope of the work carried out.

1.7 Recommendations and Future Work

Following on from the experiments and the results obtained, the DETR models showed a much better potential than the other models. However, this observation can be attributed to the non-consideration of hyperparameter tuning and optimisation during the construction and training of all the models for litter classification and detection. In the future, it is recommended that additional models and learning paradigms are explored and exploited to derive new conclusions. Hyperparameter tuning and optimisation for the construction and training of the models need to be investigated too. To allow for very robust experimental analysis, avenues of employing on-the-fly litter data need to be

investigated to mirror real-world scenarios for the automatic litter classification and detection system.

2 Review of Literature

Machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques have numerous applications in today's society. Waste management, in particular, has been attracting a lot of interest due to its close relation to image recognition. Specifically, the classification of waste is well-suited to convolutional neural networks (CNNs), a class of neural networks with several connected layers that are widely used in image recognition applications [7]. Several architectures have been proposed, with increasing improvements in the accuracy of CNNs. The ResNet family [8], DenseNet [9], EfficientNet [10] and its improved variant, EfficientNetv2 [11] have all been developed. Although EfficientNetv2 is more efficient and faster than the rest, the other architectures still have their merits and can be used to adequately classify waste.

Object detection is the task of localising and classifying objects in an image. It is typically done with two different techniques: two-stage detection or single-stage detection. Two-stage detection methods generate class-agnostic object proposals in the first stage and classify them in the second stage. One-stage architectures such as the Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) [12] and the You Only Look Once (YOLO) architecture [13, 14] provide both locations and classes for each object in a single step. EfficientDet-D2 is a single-stage object detector that improves the efficiency of object detection models through a compound scaling method [15]. Instance Segmentation is another task for automated image processing, and Mask R-CNN [16, 17], which is an extended version of Faster R-CNN [18], was introduced for this. Various deep learning algorithms have been used to detect, classify, and segment waste, with average accuracy results ranging from 22% to 99.95% [15].

Pre-trained convolutional neural networks, such as AlexNet, MobileNet, InceptionResNetV2, DenseNet, and Xception, have been used for image-based waste classification [19]. Neural networks, including fast R-CNN, SSD, YOLO, EfficientDet, Cascade R-CNN, and ATSS, have

been employed for litter detection and segmentation in different environments [15]. Also, Mask R-CNN has been used for instance segmentation, and DeepLab for semantic segmentation [20, 21]. The average mAP score for these algorithms has ranged from 15.9% to 81% [15, 19]. However, these experiments have usually focused on detecting a single type of waste in a single environment.

For the DSG challenge, the goal is to explore some of these machine-learning techniques and/or methodologies for automatic litter detection using the context provided by the COs (i.e., KWT-KSB). In particular, Mask R-CNN, Fast R-CNN, and YOLO have been employed primarily because of their popularity and several applications according to the available literature [15, 19–21].

3 Data Overview

The core datasets for the DSG challenge and the overall data quality issues are discussed and summarised as follows:

3.1 Dataset Description

Plastic pollution in marine environments continues to pose a global threat to the life of marine species, human health, coastal expenditures and tourism and even food security. It is estimated that over 350 million tons of plastic are generated annually and over 150 million tons are in water bodies (i.e., oceans) all over the world today [22, 23]. Generally, plastic (i.e., macro-plastic) degrades over time into micro-plastic and both macro-plastic and micro-plastic impact the environment negatively. It can be said that the primary source of plastic in oceans is rivers [23].

Kili's open-source plastic in river dataset allows for the exploration and exploitation of plastic detection models in mitigating or combating plastic pollution in water bodies [5]. It can be best described as a collection of labelled images curated and annotated for use in AI applications, such as equipping autonomous boats to clean rivers by identifying areas having high floating plastic densities. [5]

For emphasis, the *TACO dataset* is an open-source image dataset [1].

The images comprise waste in the wild: specifically, photos of litter taken in diverse environments. The images in the TACO dataset have been manually labelled and segmented according to a hierarchical taxonomy. In this way, it is a very good choice for the training and evaluation of object detection algorithms. [1]

The primary advantages of the TACO dataset include (but are not limited to) the following [1]:

- The use of object segmentation to overcome the limitations associated with the use of bounding boxes for certain tasks such as robotic grasping.
- Having all its images under a free licence to support the unrestricted use of the dataset in any context defined by the end users.
- Background annotations covering several tagged environments.
- Object context tag that allows for finer discrimination between what is trash and what is not trash.

The *PlastOPol dataset* [2, 3] provides a set of images with the presence of litter in several types of environments, circumventing the issue of existing litter detection datasets. This is in contrast to other popular litter detection datasets like the TACO dataset where outdoor backgrounds are not presented (an inherent limitation in the development of computational models for environmental litter detection) [1].

The PlastOPol dataset can also be best described as a collection of labelled images of plastic pollution in the environment, specifically focusing on the presence of microplastics. The dataset contains images with several occlusion, lighting, and background conditions, that go hand in hand with very challenging detection scenarios. It should be noted that these additional elements in the PlastOPol dataset make the PlastOPol dataset ideal and complete for the training and evaluation of object detection models. [2, 3]

3.2 Data Quality Issues

Even though Kili's dataset, the TACO dataset, and the PlastOPol dataset are all open-source datasets that offer curated and annotated data for

machine learning and AI applications, there are still potential data quality issues that may affect their usefulness and reliability, generally and severally in the context of the DSG challenge. Some of the data quality issues that could be associated with these datasets are enumerated as follows:

3.2.1 Bias

The data in the datasets may contain biases, such as the over-representation of certain groups or objects, which can affect the performance of machine learning algorithms trained and evaluated on the data.

3.2.2 Inaccuracy

The annotations and labels provided in the datasets may contain errors or inaccuracies, which can affect the reliability of the data and the performance of machine learning algorithms trained and evaluated on the data.

3.2.3 Inconsistency

The annotations and labels provided in the datasets may be inconsistent, either due to human error or differences in interpretation, which can lead to confusion and reduced reliability of the data.

3.2.4 Limited Diversity

The data in the datasets may be limited regarding the diversity of objects, scenes, or contexts, which can affect the generalisability and robustness of the machine learning algorithms trained and evaluated on the data.

3.2.5 Insufficient Quantity

The size of the dataset may be insufficient to train the selected machine learning algorithms to guarantee accuracy, reliability, and generalisation, especially for complex tasks.

It is important to note that the data quality issues enumerated above (Sections 3.2.1 to 3.2.5) are not peculiar to the core datasets considered for the DSG challenge (i.e., Kili's dataset, the TACO dataset, and the PlastOPol dataset). In fact, these are common challenges that arise in many datasets used for machine learning and AI applications. Hence, as carried out by the COs and the DSG participants (see Section 4.1 where a critical study of the primary dataset (the TACO dataset [1]) used for the experiments is presented), it is pertinent for researchers and developers to evaluate the quality of datasets rigorously and meticulously address any issues that may affect the reliability and usefulness of the data for their specific use cases.

3.3 Data Summary

Kili's dataset, the TACO dataset, and the PlastOPol dataset are the primary open-source datasets considered for the DSG challenge. As already discussed above, the choice of these datasets stems from the many advantages that they offer against their limitations for the training and evaluation of litter classification and detection models. It should be emphasised that such litter classification and detection models, if found to be sufficiently accurate, reliable, and generalisable, will ultimately provide a basis for the design and development of full-fledged automatic litter classification and detection systems that are machine learning-driven and/or AI-assisted. Even though any or a combination of the data quality issues enumerated above may exist, Kili's dataset, the TACO dataset, and the PlastOPol dataset offer valuable resources to researchers and developers working in the area of automatic litter detection using machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques.

4 Experiments

This Section reports on the experiments carried out for the DSG challenge. It should be emphasised here that due to the brevity of the DSG challenge, results and discussions are presented for the TACO dataset only, the focus of a considerable amount of the experimental studies for the DSG challenge.

4.1 The TACO Dataset

The TACO dataset is a crowd-sourced dataset of waste in the wild with high-resolution mobile phone images [1]. As earlier discussed, it is a growing collection of images of litter found in natural environments (e.g., forests, highways, coastlines, etc.). Through manual labelling and hierarchical taxonomy segmentation, the TACO dataset is purpose-built for training and evaluating object detection algorithms. The distribution of categories in the official TACO dataset is shown in Figure 2, with cigarette labels comprising the largest number and plastic paper bags the least. Figure 3 shows the average percentage of each element in the official TACO dataset.

4.1.1 Distribution of TACO Dataset

The TACO dataset contains 15,000 annotated images with 4,784 objects. All litter have been assigned to one of 60 classes that belong to 28 super (top) categories, including unlabelled litter for hard-to-recognise or heavily obscured objects. The annotations are provided in the well-known COCO (common objects in context) format [4] on the instance segmentation level with an extra background description - Trash, Vegetation, Sand, Water, Indoor, and Pavement.

Another advantage of the TACO dataset is that it is characterized by various litter types and a relatively high diversity of backgrounds. However, due to the crowd-sourcing nature of the dataset, the labels may contain some user-induced errors and bias, i.e., not all objects in the TACO dataset can be categorised strictly as litter because the categorisation is contextual.

4.1.2 TACO Dataset Preprocessing

For the experiments, two sets of TACO datasets were employed, with the first comprising 1,500 images and 4,784 annotations from the official annotations of the COCO type. The second set comprised 6,004 images and 18,474 annotations from the unofficially annotated TACO dataset. It should be noted that prior to investigations using YOLO, the official annotations required pre-processing into the yaml format, while both sets

of images necessitated normalisation.

4.2 Explored Machine Learning Frameworks and Models

The machine learning models explored by the DSG participants are briefly described as follows:

- *Fast R-CNN*: Fast R-CNN (fast region-based convolutional network) is a machine learning framework for object detection that premises on previous works employing R-CNN [17]. Similar to previous works, Fast R-CNN also uses deep convolutional networks; however, it improves the training and testing speed while also increasing detection accuracy [24]. More details about the Fast R-CNN framework can be found in [24].
- *Mask R-CNN*: Mask R-CNN (mask region-based convolutional network) is a flexible, easy-to-use, and general framework for object instance segmentation [16]. Typically, it works by efficiently detecting objects in an image and creating a high-quality segmentation mask for each instance at the same time [16]. It should be noted that mask R-CNN is an extension of the faster R-CNN methodology [18] through the addition of a branch for predicting an object mask simultaneously with the existing branch for bounding box recognition [16]. More details on the mask R-CNN methodology or framework can be found in [16].
- *YOLO*: YOLO (you only look once) is a novel machine-learning technique for object detection currently in its eighth version [13, 25]. In comparison to other methodologies for object detection that re-engineer classifiers to perform detection, YOLO formulates object detection as a regression problem where spatially separated bounding boxes and associated class probabilities are utilised [13]. Typically, YOLO allows a single neural network to predict bounding boxes and class probabilities directly from full images in a single evaluation [13]. More details about the YOLO framework can be found in [13].
- *DETR*: DETR (Detection with Transformers) is also a new object

detection methodology or framework that handles object detection as a direct set prediction problem [26]. It eliminates the need for many of the manually designed features available in conventional object detection methods [26]. As a result, the main elements in DETR are a set-based global loss that enforces distinct predictions through bipartite matching and a transformer encoder-decoder architecture. More details about the DETR framework can be found in [26].

4.3 Experiments and Results

4.3.1 The Environment and Experimental Setup

All datasets used for the experiments were securely stored in Turing's data safe haven after sensitivity checks and sensitivity classification. As the name suggests, Turing's data safe haven is a cloud-based environment that is secure, scalable, and reproducibly deployable to support the safe and productive utilisation of sensitive data by researchers within the Alan Turing Institute [27–29]. By openly publishing the code and documentation required to deploy, configure and manage a Data Safe Haven instance, the Alan Turing Institute has made it easier for others to deploy their own Trusted Research Environments (TREs), reducing the effort required to support their researchers in working safely with sensitive data [29].

With all the datasets for the experiments securely stored in Turing's data safe haven, the experiments for the DSG were designed and mostly implemented in Turing's TRE, where the datasets are kept secure and are only accessible following appropriate approvals and access being granted, to comply with the requirements of data providers [27, 30]. The main experimental setup involved secured access to the datasets (ingressed into the TRE) and the design, development, and the exchange of code and ideas between participants. This was moderated by the facilitators on Slack and GitHub.

4.3.2 Performance Metrics

The Mean Average Precision (mAP) was used for detection evaluation. Even though mAP, in and of itself, is not sufficient to evaluate the temporal

nature of object detection (particularly, video objects) [31], it remains a widely used metric for the appraisal of the detection accuracy of image and video detectors [32–34]. The mAP metric shows how well the predicted box fits the Ground Truth (localisation), and whether the class label is correctly predicted (classification) [35]. For each bounding box, the Intersection over Union (IoU) between the predicted bounding box and the Ground Truth was calculated; if the Area of Overlap to the Area of Union was higher than the threshold, the prediction was estimated as correct. The mAP score was averaged for all categories.

The mAP with IoU threshold 0.50 (mAP50) was used as a basic evaluation metric in the detection task. Additionally, the mAP with 0.75 IoU threshold level (mAP75) and the mAP integrated over IoUs was also used in the range from 0.5 to 0.95 with step 0.05 (AP). It should be noted that the choice of these mAP thresholds is based on inferences drawn from existing literature where similar experiments have been carried out [36–39].

For classification, the F1 score was mostly used, as it balances Precision and Recall metrics [40]. Precision shows how accurate predictions are, while Recall shows how many samples from this class were correctly predicted [41]. The F1 score is a widely used measure for uneven class distribution, which is the case in most waste datasets [42, 43].

4.3.3 DETR, and Mask R-CNN, Fast R-CNN, YOLOv7 Models

The transformer approach was applied to the waste detection task. DETR (which stands for DEtection TRansformer) with ResNet-50 and ResNet-101 backbone was initialized with pre-trained weights. In all experiments, the AdamW optimizer was used, with a learning rate set to $1e-4$ in the transformer and $1e-5$ in the backbone according to the inferences drawn from the experiments in [26]. It should be noted that these parameters can be tuned and/or optimized to determine what their near-optimal values are according to the use case. For brevity, deductive values from the available literature [26] have been used as opposed to values obtained from hyperparameter tuning and/or optimization. The selected number of queries, which represents the maximum number of instances that could be found in the image, equalled 100, the default setting. In the final tests, it was observed that after about 50 epochs, the loss values saturated (i.e., they stopped updating), and longer training did

not reduce the training nor the validation error. The DETR litter detection model is according to [44]. [26, 45]

Model	Backbone	mAP@0.5
One-class Litter		
Mask R-CNN	ResNet-50	27.6
Fast R-CNN	VGG-16	29.5
YOLOv7	EELAN	45.7
DETR	ResNet-50	51.2
6-class classification		
Mask R-CNN	ResNet-50	6.1
Fast R-CNN	VGG-16	10.7
YOLOv7	EELAN	14.3
DETR	ResNet-50	16.1

Table 3: Model performance on TACO dataset.

It should be noted that the implementation of fast R-CNN and YOLOv7 (you only look once version seven [46]) are based on the libraries in [47] and [46], respectively. In the case of instance segmentation, Mask R-CNN with ResNet-50 backbone was used. In the final tests, the model was trained for 20 epochs with a learning rate set to 1e-3 and decay set to 1e-4 based on inferences drawn from previous experiments reported in the literature [48, 49]. It should be noted that these parameters can be tuned and/or optimized to determine what their near-optimal values are according to the use case. For brevity, deductive values from the available literature ([48, 49]) have been used as opposed to values obtained from hyperparameter tuning and/or optimization. Transfer learning technique was also used in this study, as each of the models was initially pre-trained on the COCO 2017 subset. Implementation of the model is based on standard Pytorch library [50].

The mAP values for the DETR, Mask R-CNN, R-CNN, YOLOv7 models are reported in Table 3.

4.3.4 YOLOv8 Model

YOLOv8 (you only look once version eight [25]) is an advanced real-time object detection system that employs deep learning algorithms to accurately detect objects in images or videos. It is a variant (the most recent version, specifically) of the original YOLO [13]. The system comprises a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture that utilises anchor boxes and feature maps to facilitate the detection of objects of varying shapes and sizes. YOLOv8 is trained on large datasets, enabling it to identify a broad range of objects, including people, animals, vehicles, and household items. The system's high efficiency and rapid image processing capabilities make it well-suited for real-time applications, such as video surveillance, autonomous driving, and robotics. Due to its superior capabilities, YOLOv8 represents a state-of-the-art object detection system and is extensively utilised in both research and industry for diverse applications. [13, 14, 25]

YOLOv8 utilises a variety of performance evaluation metrics to gauge its accuracy and efficacy in object detection tasks. These metrics comprise precision, recall, and mean average precision (mAP). Mean average precision (mAP) is a widely adopted metric for evaluating object detection systems as established earlier (see Section 4.3.2). It quantifies the average precision over all feasible recall values. The mAP score is calculated by averaging the precision values at different recall levels for each class. YOLOv8 also utilises other performance evaluation metrics, such as Intersection over Union (IoU), which measures the extent of overlap between predicted and ground truth bounding boxes, and F1 score, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall.

Figure 4 displays the performance evaluation of YOLOv8 on an unofficially labelled dataset, while Figure 5 presents the outcomes of a test set sample that was employed to evaluate our model's object detection capabilities on images. From Figures 4 and 5, it can be seen that the YOLOv8 is also promising for the litter classification and detection task.

4.3.5 YOLOv5 Model

YOLOv5 (you look only look once version five [51]) is an improved version of the original YOLO model [13]. It is a very stable version of YOLO and it

has features such as integrated experiment tracking, hyperparameter optimization, and automatic export to popular export formats [25, 51]. The YOLOv5 model was trained and tested on the TACO dataset. The dataset was converted and downloaded in the appropriate format as a yaml file (i.e., YOLOv5 PyTorch TXT format). The training set contained 4,200 images, the validation set contained 1,700 images and the test set contained 100 images. The model was trained for 100 epochs using the default settings for all hyperparameters.

Using the F1 curve (see Figure 6), the balance between precision and recall can be visualised. From Figure 6, it can be seen that the cup, can, aluminium foil, and bottle cap categories are best detected with the highest F1 scores. On the other hand, broken glass is not well detected by the model and has the lowest curve on the plot. The precision vs recall graph (see Figure 7) corroborates this observation.

From the confusion matrix (see Figure 8), it can be observed that for many categories of litter, the model falsely predicts the litter as background objects. Broken glass, pop tabs, and cigarettes have the highest rates of being misclassified as background objects, while cups, cans, aluminium foil, bottle caps, and plastic bag wrappers have the highest rate of being correctly classified.

5 Future Work and Research Avenues

Future work will focus on further tuning the models investigated in the present study to enhance performance. In addition to this, the size of the available open-source datasets will be augmented by integrating Kili's and PlastOPol datasets, alongside the TACO and the synthetic datasets to increase the overall amount of available data. The enhanced models will then be applied to the augmented or increased dataset to improve the model's accuracy.

To address the issue of litter classification and detection, it should be noted that a two-stage approach has been proposed, where the first stage involves detecting a single class of litter, while the second stage involves a multi-class classification on the detected litter, incorporating a filtering function based on the model's confidence scores. To make this

methodology more robust, a separate model for dog fouling and graffiti datasets will be constructed and trained, which will subsequently be combined with the main model to improve the overall model's performance. It is envisaged that ensemble learning methods will likely be adopted to guarantee the practicality of this robust methodology.

To evaluate the efficacy of the model obtained in the future as a result of the above experiments, the model's performance will be assessed on a street survey dataset (e.g., the test data prepared by KWT-KSB (see Section 1.2.5)). Alongside the model performance assessment using the street survey dataset, semi-supervised learning techniques such as a merger of clustering and classification will also be applied to the unannotated dataset, aiming to enhance the model's multi-class classification capabilities.

Litter detection and classification through machine learning is a promising approach to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of identifying litter in the environment for effective waste management. By adopting this technology, the negative impacts of waste on wildlife and human health can be mitigated, and waste management in various settings, including public spaces, residential areas, and industrial sites, can be improved.

The implementation of machine learning technology in environmental conservation is a crucial step toward sustainable waste management. By leveraging the power of machine learning algorithms, litter detection, and classification can be accomplished with high accuracy and efficiency, enabling effective waste management strategies to be developed and implemented.

The use of machine learning for litter classification and detection has the potential to revolutionise waste management practices by enabling faster and more accurate identification of litter. This can help to minimise the negative environmental impact of waste and reduce the risk of contamination to human health. As such, the adoption of machine learning in environmental conservation is an important and timely endeavour that holds great promise for enhancing the sustainability of our planet.

6 Conclusions

To address the DSG challenge, the TACO dataset has been used as a case study for the testing and validation of selected machine learning frameworks (Fast R-CNN, Mask R-CNN, YOLO and DETR) that can support litter detection in the context provided by the COs (i.e., KWT-KSB). As a result, the experiments carried out and reported on constitute the preliminary phase of a much broader scope of work that will involve more datasets and the co-use of several machine learning frameworks to have a robust automatic litter detection system. The models built and trained by the Mask R-CNN, Fast R-CNN, YOLO, and DETR object detection and classification frameworks provided useful practical insights that automatic litter detection is feasible to a reasonable extent using these methods based on their mAP metrics and the F1 score for the YOLO model. However, it should be noted that the mAP metrics and F1 scores for all the models may not be truly representative of the models' fitness for the object detection and classification task. This is primarily because the control parameters or hyperparameters of the methods used for model construction, training, and testing were neither tuned nor optimized in all the experiments. So, based on an educated guess, the models' performance metrics can be expected to be relatively higher than the values reported here in the event of hyperparameter tuning and optimization. This limitation and other limitations such as the use of only a single waste dataset (i.e., the TACO dataset) all point to the fact that the experiments detailed in this report are not exhaustive, due to the brevity of the DSG challenge. In the future, given more time and resources, a much more robust experimental framework that will involve the iterative training, testing, and validation of the models is expected to be carried out under various conditions that will involve a multiplicity of datasets, and an ensemble of machine learning techniques or frameworks whose control parameters are tuned and optimized to have better and more robust models.

7 Team members

Fazl Barez is Ph.D. student at the University of Edinburgh and the University of Oxford. Fazl contributed to the DSG challenge by

contributing to the literature review and summary section as well as the initial discussion on what methods to use.

Hao Ni is Ph.D. student at the University of Birmingham. Hao contributed to the DSG challenge by exploring and pre-processing the TACO dataset and labelling the images to fit the different models. And, he put the data into YOLOv8 for testing and reported on the obtained results.

Samuel Fielding is a Ph.D. researcher at the University of Edinburgh and an intern with the Alan Turing Institute in association with Keep Wales Tidy and Keep Scotland Beautiful. He contributed to this project by transferring and preparing the datasets and providing initial thoughts on the direction of the project.

Attiq Rehman is a Computer Vision engineer. He contributed to this project by experimenting with the dataset with deep learning models for object detection.

Oladapo Babajide is a data scientist. He was one of the project facilitators who ensured that the DSG challenge participants adhered to all requirements from the principal investigators.

Maitri H. Modi is a data scientist. She was one of the project facilitators who ensured that the DSG challenge participants adhered to all requirements from the principal investigators.

Mobayode O. Akinsolu is a Chartered Engineer, a Fellow of the HEA, a Senior Member of the IEEE, and a Registered Electrical Engineer with the COREN. He is currently a Senior Lecturer in Electronic and Communication Engineer. He was the Principal Investigator for the KWT-KSB DSG challenge.

References

- [1] P. F. Proença and P. Simoes, "Taco: Trash annotations in context for litter detection," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.06975*, 2020.
- [2] M. Córdova, A. Pinto, C. C. Hellevik, S. A.-A. Alaliyat, I. A. Hameed, H. Pedrini, and R. d. S. Torres, "Litter detection with deep learning: A comparative study," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 2, p. 548, 2022.

- [3] M. Córdova, A. Pinto, C. C. Hellevik, S. A.-A. Alaliyat, I. A. Hameed, H. Pedrini, and R. d. S. Torres, “Plastopol: A dataset for litter detection,” Jan 2022.
- [4] “COCO (Common Objects in Context).” <https://cocodataset.org/#home>. Accessed: 2023-01-05.
- [5] “Kili’s Community Challenge - Plastic in River dataset.” <https://kili-technology.com/data-labeling/machine-learning/kili-s-community-challenge-plastic-in-river-dataset>. Accessed: 2023-16-03.
- [6] X. Dong, Z. Yu, W. Cao, Y. Shi, and Q. Ma, “A survey on ensemble learning,” *Frontiers of Computer Science*, vol. 14, pp. 241–258, 2020.
- [7] W.-L. Mao, W.-C. Chen, C.-T. Wang, and Y.-H. Lin, “Recycling waste classification using optimized convolutional neural network,” *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, vol. 164, p. 105132, 2021.
- [8] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, “Deep residual learning for image recognition,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1512.03385*, 2016.
- [9] G. Huang, D. Chen, T. Li, F. Wu, L. Van Der Maaten, and K. Q. Weinberger, “Multi-scale dense networks for resource efficient image classification,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1703.09844*, 2017.
- [10] G. Huang, Z. Liu, L. van der Maaten, and K. Q. Weinberger, “Densely connected convolutional networks,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1608.06993*, 2017.
- [11] M. Tan and Q. Le, “Efficientnet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks,” in *International conference on machine learning*, pp. 6105–6114, PMLR, 2019.
- [12] W. Liu, D. Anguelov, D. Erhan, C. Szegedy, S. Reed, C.-Y. Fu, and A. C. Berg, “Ssd: Single shot multibox detector,” in *Computer Vision—ECCV 2016: 14th European Conference, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, October 11–14, 2016, Proceedings, Part I 14*, pp. 21–37, Springer, 2016.
- [13] J. Redmon, S. Divvala, R. Girshick, and A. Farhadi, “You only look once: Unified, real-time object detection,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE*

- conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pp. 779–788, 2016.
- [14] P. Jiang, D. Ergu, F. Liu, Y. Cai, and B. Ma, “A review of YOLO algorithm developments,” *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 199, pp. 1066–1073, 2022.
 - [15] S. Majchrowska, A. Mikołajczyk, M. Ferlin, Z. Klawikowska, M. A. Plantykov, A. Kwasigroch, and K. Majek, “Deep learning-based waste detection in natural and urban environments,” *Waste Management*, vol. 138, pp. 274–284, 2022.
 - [16] K. He, G. Gkioxari, P. Dollár, and R. Girshick, “Mask r-cnn,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, pp. 2961–2969, 2017.
 - [17] P. Bharati and A. Pramanik, “Deep learning techniques—r-cnn to mask r-cnn: a survey,” *Computational Intelligence in Pattern Recognition: Proceedings of CIPR 2019*, pp. 657–668, 2020.
 - [18] S. Ren, K. He, R. Girshick, and J. Sun, “Faster r-cnn: Towards real-time object detection with region proposal networks,” *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 28, 2015.
 - [19] O. Tamin, E. G. Mounq, J. A. Dargham, F. Yahya, S. Omatu, and L. Angeline, “Machine learning for plastic waste detection: State-of-the-art, challenges, and solutions,” in *2022 International Conference on Communications, Information, Electronic and Energy Systems (CIEES)*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2022.
 - [20] P. Jaikumar, R. Vandaele, and V. Ojha, “Transfer learning for instance segmentation of waste bottles using mask r-cnn algorithm,” in *Intelligent Systems Design and Applications: 20th International Conference on Intelligent Systems Design and Applications (ISDA 2020) held December 12-15, 2020*, pp. 140–149, Springer, 2021.
 - [21] J. Tian, J. Yuan, and H. Liu, “Road marking detection based on mask r-cnn instance segmentation model,” in *2020 international conference on computer vision, image and deep learning (CVIDL)*, pp. 246–249, IEEE, 2020.

- [22] A. Bratovic, “Degradation of micro-and nano-plastics by photocatalytic methods,” *J Nanosci Nanotechnol Appl*, vol. 3, p. 206, 2019.
- [23] E. Kosior and I. Crescenzi, “Solutions to the plastic waste problem on land and in the oceans,” in *Plastic waste and recycling*, pp. 415–446, Elsevier, 2020.
- [24] R. Girshick, “Fast r-cnn,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, pp. 1440–1448, 2015.
- [25] “YOLOv8 Docs.” <https://docs.ultralytics.com/>. Accessed: 2023-16-03.
- [26] N. Carion, F. Massa, G. Synnaeve, N. Usunier, A. Kirillov, and S. Zagoruyko, “End-to-end object detection with transformers,” in *Computer Vision–ECCV 2020: 16th European Conference, Glasgow, UK, August 23–28, 2020, Proceedings, Part I 16*, pp. 213–229, Springer, 2020.
- [27] “Data safe havens in the cloud.” <https://www.turing.ac.uk/research/research-projects/data-safe-havens-cloud>. Accessed: 2023-22-05.
- [28] D. Arenas, J. Atkins, C. Austin, D. Beavan, A. C. Egea, S. Carlyle-Davies, I. Carter, R. Clarke, J. Cunningham, T. Doel, *et al.*, “Design choices for productive, secure, data-intensive research at scale in the cloud,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1908.08737*, 2019.
- [29] “alan-turing-institute/data-safe-haven.” <https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/data-safe-haven>. Accessed: 2023-22-05.
- [30] E. Chalstrey, “Developing and publishing code for trusted research environments: Best practices and ways of working,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2111.06301*, 2021.
- [31] H. Mao, X. Yang, and W. J. Dally, “A delay metric for video object detection: What average precision fails to tell,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pp. 573–582, 2019.

- [32] X. Wang, M. Yang, S. Zhu, and Y. Lin, "Regionlets for generic object detection," in *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, pp. 17–24, 2013.
- [33] M. Oquab, L. Bottou, I. Laptev, and J. Sivic, "Is object localization for free?-weakly-supervised learning with convolutional neural networks," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pp. 685–694, 2015.
- [34] R. J. Wang, X. Li, and C. X. Ling, "Pelee: A real-time object detection system on mobile devices," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 31, 2018.
- [35] N. Pereira, "Pereiraasnet: Asl letter recognition with yolox taking mean average precision and inference time considerations," in *2022 2nd International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Signal Processing (AISP)*, pp. 1–6, 2022.
- [36] Y. Li, S. Li, H. Du, L. Chen, D. Zhang, and Y. Li, "Yolo-acn: Focusing on small target and occluded object detection," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 227288–227303, 2020.
- [37] T. Truong, A. Bhatt, L. Queiroz, K. Lai, and S. Yanushkevich, "Instance segmentation of personal protective equipment using a multi-stage transfer learning process," in *2020 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*, pp. 1181–1186, 2020.
- [38] H. Su, S. Wei, M. Yan, C. Wang, J. Shi, and X. Zhang, "Object detection and instance segmentation in remote sensing imagery based on precise mask r-cnn," in *IGARSS 2019 - 2019 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, pp. 1454–1457, 2019.
- [39] Z. Hu, H. Yang, and T. Lou, "Dual attention-guided feature pyramid network for instance segmentation of group pigs," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 186, p. 106140, 2021.
- [40] F. Morstatter, L. Wu, T. H. Nazer, K. M. Carley, and H. Liu, "A new approach to bot detection: Striking the balance between precision and recall," in *2016 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining (ASONAM)*, pp. 533–540, 2016.

- [41] A. O. Sangodoyin, M. O. Akinsolu, P. Pillai, and V. Grout, "Detection and classification of ddos flooding attacks on software-defined networks: A case study for the application of machine learning," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 122495–122508, 2021.
- [42] A. Patrizi, G. Gambosi, and F. M. Zanzotto, "Data augmentation using background replacement for automated sorting of littered waste," *Journal of imaging*, vol. 7, no. 8, p. 144, 2021.
- [43] T. Ji, H. Fang, R. Zhang, J. Yang, L. Fan, Y. Hu, and Z. Cai, "Low-value recyclable waste identification based on nir feature analysis and rgb-nir fusion," *Infrared Physics & Technology*, p. 104693, 2023.
- [44] "Facebook Research / DETR." <https://github.com/facebookresearch/detr>. Accessed: 2023-16-03.
- [45] A. Gupta, S. Narayan, K. Joseph, S. Khan, F. S. Khan, and M. Shah, "Ow-DETR: Open-world detection transformer," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 9235–9244, 2022.
- [46] "Ultralytics/YOLOv7." <https://github.com/WongKinYiu/yolov7>. Accessed: 2023-16-03.
- [47] "FAST R-CNN." <https://github.com/rbgirshick/fast-rcnn>. Accessed: 2023-16-03.
- [48] S. Aparna, K. Muppavaram, C. C. Ramayanam, and K. S. S. Ramani, "Mask rcnn with resnet50 for dental filling detection," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 12, no. 10, 2021.
- [49] M. E. Sahin, H. Ulutas, E. Yuce, and M. F. Erkoc, "Detection and classification of covid-19 by using faster r-cnn and mask r-cnn on ct images," *Neural Computing and Applications*, pp. 1–15, 2023.
- [50] "Mask R-CNN." https://pytorch.org/vision/main/models/mask_rcnn.html. Accessed: 2023-16-03.
- [51] "Ultralytics/YOLOv5." <https://github.com/ultralytics/yolov5>. Accessed: 2023-16-03.

Figure 1: Annotations in the TACO dataset [1].

Figure 2: Category distribution in the TACO dataset ([1]).

Figure 3: Proportion or distribution of images by background tag in the TACO dataset [1].

Model summary (fused): 168 layers, 3009158 parameters, 0 gradients, 8.1 GFLOPs

Class	Images	Instances	Box(P	R	mAP50	m
all	1704	4830	0.347	0.25	0.208	0.155
Aluminium foil	1704	62	0.357	0.323	0.261	0.204
Bottle cap	1704	459	0.389	0.56	0.47	0.343
Bottle	1704	320	0.576	0.285	0.331	0.219
Broken glass	1704	123	1	0	0.00101	0.000287
Can	1704	267	0.308	0.539	0.422	0.32
Carton	1704	263	0.281	0.418	0.303	0.245
Cigarette	1704	565	0.316	0.0212	0.0298	0.0147
Cup	1704	186	0.302	0.392	0.32	0.243
Lid	1704	93	0.415	0.312	0.28	0.229
Other litter	1704	178	0.199	0.135	0.0954	0.0687
Other plastic	1704	265	0.19	0.0906	0.0736	0.047
Paper	1704	178	0.215	0.142	0.0866	0.0669
Plastic bag - wrapper	1704	854	0.328	0.477	0.352	0.233
Plastic container	1704	90	0.38	0.259	0.236	0.201
Pop tab	1704	125	0.203	0.072	0.057	0.0328
Straw	1704	120	0.283	0.217	0.155	0.102
Styrofoam piece	1704	113	0.254	0.221	0.201	0.179
Unlabeled litter	1704	569	0.253	0.0404	0.0674	0.0353

Speed: 0.3ms preprocess, 1.2ms inference, 0.0ms loss, 1.2ms postprocess per image

Figure 4: A typical result for YOLOv8.

Figure 5: A typical task example for YOLOv8.

Figure 6: F1 Curve

Figure 7: Precision recall curve.

Figure 8: Confusion matrix.

Figure 9: Metrics through training.

Class	Images	Labels	P	R	mAP@.5	mAP@.5:.95	100% 54/54 [00:33<00:00, 1.6iit/s]
all	1704	4830	0.447	0.267	0.265	0.162	
Aluminium foil	1704	62	0.676	0.387	0.405	0.284	
Bottle cap	1704	459	0.438	0.466	0.434	0.263	
Bottle	1704	320	0.58	0.347	0.393	0.229	
Broken glass	1704	123	0.327	0.0894	0.0681	0.0239	
Can	1704	267	0.52	0.532	0.547	0.343	
Carton	1704	263	0.464	0.323	0.321	0.201	
Cigarette	1704	565	0.395	0.103	0.112	0.0426	
Cup	1704	186	0.499	0.468	0.457	0.3	
Lid	1704	93	0.715	0.247	0.309	0.209	
Other litter	1704	178	0.363	0.196	0.178	0.1	
Other plastic	1704	265	0.352	0.192	0.182	0.103	
Paper	1704	178	0.436	0.287	0.245	0.168	
Plastic bag - wrapper	1704	854	0.434	0.445	0.403	0.227	
Plastic container	1704	90	0.37	0.156	0.161	0.112	
Pop tab	1704	125	0.256	0.056	0.0514	0.03	
Straw	1704	120	0.294	0.167	0.135	0.065	
Styrofoam piece	1704	113	0.494	0.204	0.205	0.144	
Unlabeled litter	1704	569	0.428	0.151	0.155	0.0764	

Figure 10: mAP for each category.

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

**turing.ac.uk
@turinginst**